

Myelomeningocele-Associated Hydrocephalus: A Study from North-Central Nigeria.

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Article information

Date Submitted: 04/04/2024

Date Accepted: 05/05/2024

Date Published: 25/06/2024

ABSTRACT

Objective: Hydrocephalus remains one of the most common complications of myelomeningocele, and may be present at birth or be quiescent and develop after the repair of myelomeningocele. Myelomeningocele being a severe central nervous system anomaly that is compatible with life, throws multiple morbidity challenges that requires care, and attention to its most core and central association-hydrocephalus, in other to ameliorate the associated sufferings. Hence, our aim was to review the management of hydrocephalus in patients with myelomeningocele at our Centre. **Methods:** A retrospective study was conducted, involving all children who underwent open myelomeningocele repair in a tertiary Centre in North-Central Nigeria between January, 2016 and December, 2023. Case folders were reviewed on all children meeting the inclusion criteria of all patients with the condition treated during the study period. **Results:** one hundred and three patients underwent myelomeningocele repair. Thirteen had ventriculoperitoneal shunts inserted, being the primary means of cerebrospinal fluid diversion. No endoscopic third ventriculostomy was performed and no external ventricular drain was applied. The lumbosacral region constituted the anatomical area most involved in myelomeningocele. **Conclusion:** For proper care, good outcomes, and quality of life for patients with myelomeningoceles, excellent hydrocephalus care is a prime consideration notwithstanding the low rate of occurrence of myelomeningocele-associated hydrocephalus in our study.

Keywords: Spina bifida, Myelomeningocele, Hydrocephalus, Ventriculoperitoneal Shunt, Endoscopic Third Ventriculostomy (ETV), External Ventricular Drain (EVD), North-Central Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Myelomeningocele, MM, is the most common congenital anomaly of the central nervous system and the most severe birth defect compatible with long-term survival.¹ It has an incidence ranging between

0.2 and 2 per 1000 live births in the USA.² The survival rate for patients with myelomeningocele used to be about 10% in the 1950s.³ But today, such patients survive into adulthood because of advances in the management of several important complications

How to cite this article

*JO Obande, EI Obande. Myelomeningocele-Associated Hydrocephalus: A Study from North-Central Nigeria. J Biomed Res Clin Pract: 2024;7(2):00-00. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13644632>

Access to the article

Website: <http://www.jbrcp.org>

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13644632](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13644632)

associated with this complex disease, such as hydrocephalus.^{4,6}

The association between myelomeningoceles and hydrocephalus is well established. The development of hydrocephalus is a major problem for the majority of patients with myelomeningocele, as hydrocephalus was generally regarded as a death sentence as a result of severe handicap due to brain atrophy.⁷ Most infants who develop symptomatic hydrocephalus do so prenatally or within the first few days or weeks following myelomeningocele repair, with >80% eventually needing a surgical procedure to treat the condition,⁸⁻¹⁰ as it complicates 35–91% of myelomeningocele.^{11,12} The rate of treated hydrocephalus in patients with myelomeningocele varies with the anatomic level of the lesion, being 60.7% for sacral, 82.4% for lumbar, and 92.2% for thoracic.¹² The mechanism linking the level of the MM to the likelihood of shunting is assumed to be as a result of greater meningeal contamination with amniotic fluid, greater loss of cerebrospinal fluid, CSF, pulsatility at the cranial level, and that high-level and low-level MM are two different entities, resulting from defects at different stages of the closure of the neural tube.¹³

Aetiology and Pathogenesis of Myelomeningocele-associated Hydrocephalus

The etiology of hydrocephalus in patients with myelomeningocele has been widely studied, yet its pathogenesis unclear.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ It is known that several obstructive and absorptive factors act together to cause hydrocephalus in patients with myelomeningocele. However, the most widely accepted theory for the development of hydrocephalus in patients with myelomeningocele is the unified theory by McLone and Knepper in 1989.¹⁴ Their hypothesis, postulates that the embryological basis of the Chiari II is the loss of CSF through the open spinal defect, resulting in impairment in the development of the brain and normal CSF pathways, and ultimately permits for the caudal descent of the hindbrain and subsequent hydrocephalus development.

Treatment

The foundation of all the problems in myelomeningocele (MM) occurs from a development anomaly of the nervous system with the most clinically obvious problem involving the caudal spinal cord.¹⁷ But, the entire nervous system is affected.¹⁷ Neurosurgical challenges are central in the care of patients with myelomeningocele, as all dysraphism associated morbidities result from impaired neurologic control of other involved body systems. Though, neurologic challenges may be at the core, the fundamental anomalies cannot be surgically reversed and so all treatments are ameliorative to prevent further complications.¹⁷ Despite current improvements in neurosurgical care for patients with spina bifida five key thematic questions remain in the following areas: 1) In utero closure of MMC, 2) Optimal management of hydrocephalus/closure, 3) Treatment of the Chiari II malformation, 4) Management of the symptomatically tethered spinal cord, 5) Transitional care to adulthood and neurosurgical care for adults with spina bifida.

Our study is a foray into the second thematic question in our environment. With the introduction of the Holter valve for the ventriculo-peritoneal (VP) shunt in the 1950s, a new opportunity of the possibility for long-term survival in patients with MM opened up.¹⁸ The VP shunt has been successful in extending the life span of patients with hydrocephalus. Currently, other procedures being performed as alternatives to the VP shunt include endoscopic third ventriculostomy with and without choroid plexus cauterization.^{19,20} Bearing in mind that hydrocephalus is only one complication associated with myelomeningocele, optimal treatment of this complex disease requires multispecialty care to prevent, monitor, and treat a variety of potential health issues that impact function, quality of life, and survival.²¹ The overall aim of this paper is to review the management of hydrocephalus in patients with myelomeningocele at our Centre.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Patients and methods

All of the pediatric patients who presented with myelomeningocele between January 2016, and

December, 2023, over 7 years period, and underwent treatment for MM at University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Abuja, were registered on the operation registry of division of neurosurgery. The following data were collected from the retrospective review of patient records: demographic findings; sex and age at operation; ventriculoperitoneal shunt insertion; performance of endoscopic third ventriculostomy (ETV) or external ventricular drain (EVD) use; antibiotics used for perioperative prophylaxis; etiology of hydrocephalus related to level of MM; cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) culture results; and treatment modality. It was the protocol of the Neurosurgery division to obtain intraoperative CSF specimen for microbiologic culture analysis at all ventriculoperitoneal operations.

RESULTS

103 patients were treated for myelomeningocele during the study period. The patients ranged in age from 1 day to 3650 days old with a median age of 15 days and a sex ratio of 53.4% male to 46.6% female. Perioperative antibiotics was used for all patients and consisted of Ceftriazone (Rocephin®) at induction of anaesthesia. CSF culture results of all intraoperative specimens were all negative. Table 1 summarizes other clinical variables.

DISCUSSIONS

Most infants born with MM present for neurosurgical care at birth for treatment of the obvious spinal anomaly and oftentimes with need for hydrocephalus treatment as well or soon after.^{22,23} Surgical excision and repair of the MM attempts to reestablish anatomical layers of the midline back that have become fused in the embryonal defect and so the closure techniques have more or less not changed over several generations. Ventriculoperitoneal shunt insertion remains the cornerstone of treatment for hydrocephalus in our environment, and even in infants with spina bifida. However, in more economically-endowed nations there are active interrogations and research surrounding the optimal thresholds for initiating hydrocephalus treatment and the evolving role of endoscopic third ventriculostomy with choroid plexus coagulation.²⁴⁻

Table 1: Patients Clinical Variables

Variables	Frequency(N=103)	Percent
Sex		
Male	55	53.4
Female	48	46.6
Complications		
Hydrocephalus at birth		
Yes	6	5.8
No	97	94.2
Hydrocephalus post repair		
Yes	7	7.2
No	90	92.8
Hydrocephalus status (Total)		
With Hydrocephalus	13	12.6
Without Hydrocephalus	90	87.4
Hydrocephalus based on location of MM	n=13	
Sacral	1	7.7
Lumbar	3	23.1
Lumbosacral	9	69.2
UV Prolapse		
Yes	1	1.0
No	102	99.0
Treatment Modality	Received	
a) Excision and repair + Fixation of prolapse	1	1.0
b) Excision and repair + Ventriculo peritoneal shunt	6	5.8
c) Ventriculoperitoneal shunt	7	6.8
d) Excision and repair	89	86.4
e) Excision and repair + External Ventricular Drain (EVD)	0	0
f) Excision and repair + Endoscopic 3rd Ventriculostomy (ETV)	0	0

²⁶From our study all 7 patients with hydrocephalus at birth had ventriculoperitoneal shunt insertion. This constitutes 6.8%. It has been remarked that up to 80% of patients with MM will require the need for ventriculoperitoneal shunt insertion²⁷, which was not the case in our study. Perhaps, the threshold for shunt insertion in the developed economies was minimal. The finding from this study concurs with the concept of elevated thresholds for shunt placement due to the frequent and problematic natural history of shunts and its morbidity of repeated shunt operations and infections.¹⁷ Effective shunts therefore, can save thousands of lives despite the associated real or perceived morbidity including the presence of hydrocephalus putting an extra strain on an already malformed and poorly myelinated brainstem and consequent deterioration from the Chiari

malformation. On the other hand, shunt failure in later life may precipitate signs of tethered cord or again, Chiari malformation.

Endoscopic third ventriculostomy, as popularized by Warf et al, has a low success rate of 36% alone but this becomes improved to 76% if choroid plexus cauterization is added.^{28, 29} In a study from Portugal by Joana Rei et al, they found a success rate of 44.4% with only ETV.³⁰ Our patients had no exposure to either endoscopic third ventriculostomy or choroid plexus cauterization. This is on account of non-availability of same in our service. The attractiveness of this modality of treatment lies with the non-utilization of a foreign body along with its possible complications, much lower risk of postoperative infection, and a more physiological means of CSF drainage.³¹ EVD is used in MM in the setting of active or suspected wound infection when ventriculoperitoneal shunt is indicated. McDowell and colleagues have found that patients with an EVD or shunt placed at the time of MM closure had no wound complications in their study.³² In our study no patient had any need for EVD placement. Finnegan and his colleagues in Ireland utilized EVD for a different purpose in MM management. EVD was used to aid management of wound closure. Their finding was very interesting as when compared to the cohort in whom an EVD was not inserted at the time of surgery in the study, there was a decrease in the rate of infections. However, there was an increased rate of wound dehiscence/leak and a later need for VP shunt insertion.³³

While the connection between myelomeningoceles and hydrocephalus is widely acknowledged, the data relating to how the functional and anatomical-lesion level of the myelomeningocele impacts the necessity for hydrocephalus treatment is few. One retrospective study involving 297 patients revealed that the likelihood of requiring a shunt is dependent on both the functional and anatomical level of the myelomeningocele, where higher rates of shunting are observed in more caudal location.³⁴ But, the retrospective analysis of 72 patients by Phillips and colleagues did not find any difference in shunting rates when the anatomical level is considered.³⁵ Of 13 (12.6%) patients in our study who had

hydrocephalus, the lumbosacral region constituted the anatomical region with the highest rate of hydrocephalus occurrence, accounting for 69.2%, lumbar 23.1 and sacral 7.7%. No thoracic MM was encountered at this time. Our study overall is in concordance with the general finding of a greater occurrence of hydrocephalus with rostral located lesions. Conversely, Kim and Colleagues have contrasting findings of 60.7% for sacral, 82.4% for lumbar, and 92.2% for thoracic. The nationwide analysis and systematic review of myelomeningocele-associated hydrocephalus study from the USA by David and Colleagues authoritatively elucidated on this theme the more. From a Nationwide Inpatient Sample (NIS) database of the years 1998–2014, where a total of 10,627 inpatient MM repairs were done and 8233 (77.5%) had hydrocephalus. The hydrocephalus rates by levels were: lumbar 85.5%, thoracic 4.9%, cervical 0.5%, and unspecified 9.1%.²

Relating to perioperative occurrence of hydrocephalus, of the 13 patients who were treated for hydrocephalus, 6 (46.2%) presented with hydrocephalus and so had combined surgical intervention of ventriculoperitoneal shunt insertion and excision and repairs of MM. While the remainder of 7 (53.8%) developed hydrocephalus following the surgical repair of MM and so had another surgery. As corroborated by the study by Ashish and Colleagues,³⁶ single-stage repair of spina bifida with hydrocephalus offers considerable advantage by way of a reduction in hospital costs, burden and patient morbidity, particularly, in resource-constrained settings.

CONCLUSIONS

Excellence in hydrocephalus management in MM is the fulcrum for proper care, good outcomes, and quality of life for patients. Hydrocephalus remains the one neurologic comorbidity that is central to the well-being or can affect so many other processes and is readily available for management in MM. We found a surprisingly low rate of treated hydrocephalus occurring with myelomeningocele, being 12.6%. As no neurosurgical procedure can correct the fundamental problem, support of neurologic function by closing the initial defect and improving CSF balance is cardinal. A

consideration towards a single-stage combined repair and shunt insertion will afford reduction of hospital burden and patient morbidity.

Informed Consent

This was a retrospective review of managed patients from our database.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Joseph O Obande: Conceptualization, writing, review & editing

Elizabeth I Obande: Formal analysis- review & editing.

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